

Properties of ferromagnetic and magnetorheological fluids prepared with medium of polyethylene glycol

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1. Introduction

In general, functional particles can be prepared by conjugating organic matters to an inorganic core. Magnetite nanoparticles of the inverted spinel structure for ferromagnetic fluids have attracted much attention owing to their interesting magnetic properties and potential applications[1]. The magnetic nanoparticles are fluidized with outlayered hydrophilic or hydrophobic surfactants, and the resulting colloidal solution can be localized at a specific site under a magnetic or electromagnetic field[2]. The properties of those nanoparticles are mostly characteristic of superparamagnetism[3]. Magnetorheological fluids include the magnetic particles of high permeability dispersed in the medium of low permeability. Such colloids behavior as Newtonian fluid with isotropic mechanical property in the non-applied magnetic field, whereas they behavior as Bingham fluid of anisotropy in the applied magnetic field, forming a fibril structure by polarization of the particles in the field direction. Therefore, the viscosity of the fluids can be reversibly controlled correspondingly to the strength of applied field, in which the yield stress is developed by resisting to the shear of fluid[4].

The magnetite nanoparticles of ferromagnetic fluid was chemically prepared by coprecipitation. A micrometer-sized sendust powder of Fe-6.5wt%Si alloy was milled down to the size of nanometer for fine particles of magnetorheological fluid. Selected

oleic acid and polyethylene glycol(PEG) were used as a surfactant to adsorb on the particle surface and as a medium to disperse the adsorbed particles, respectively. The PEG has an chemical affinity for fatty acids and also is high in the boiling point and the viscosity and very low in the vapor pressure compared with water for hydrophilic fluids. The viscosity of ferromagnetic and magnetorheological fluids was measured and their shear strength was evaluated.

2. Experimental

FeCl₂·4H₂O (0.00865 mol: 1.72 g) and FeCl₃·6H₂O (0.0173 mol: 4.70 g) with a stoichiometric ratio of Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ = 0.5 were solved in 80 ml of distilled water. The precipitate of magnetic iron oxide was obtained by adding excessive ammonia water (purity 28~30 %) by 1.5 times (7 ml) of the proper quantity to the mixed solution heated to 80 °C with stirring for 1 h at 300 rpm. The black precipitate was washed five times with magnetic decantation until the pH value reached around 8. 65 ml of PEG (H(OCH₂CH₂)_nOH, average M_w 200) was poured to the gel which was dried to 100 °C. The stable colloid was prepared by stirring the solution of particles for 1 h at 300 rpm with 1.4 ml of oleic acid (CH₃(CH₂)₇CH=CH(CH₂)₇COOH, M_w 282.47, pure 90 %). The colloid volume was about 80 ml when cooled to room temperature. The process for preparing the ferromagnetic fluids is shown in Fig. 1.

The Fe-6.5wt%Si alloy powder fabricated by high-pressure water spray method at Nippon Atomized Metal Powder Corporation was used as the starting material. The powder particles are practically spherical with the size of approximately 15 μm . First, the shape of the powder particles was controlled from sphere to flake by attrition milling for 60 h at 600 rpm, in which the weight rate of zirconia ball of $\Phi 5$ mm size, raw material and ethanol was in order of 10:1:5. The attrition-milled powder was heat-treated for 1 h at 550 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in an oil-diffused vacuum furnace and then was re-milled for 5 h at 500 rpm with much the same packing rate as in attrition milling using high-energy ball mill which was charged with the mixed balls of $\Phi 2$ and $\Phi 3$ mm[5]. However, the particles of only metal components are not bondable in polar with organic compounds. Therefore, the surface of the metal particles was oxidized with trimethylamine N-oxide dehydrate (TMANO: $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{NO}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, M_w 111.14), followed by the same process as the ferromagnetic fluid to prepare the magnetorheological fluid.

Fig. 1. A process flow for ferromagnetic fluids prepared with coprecipitated magnetite particles, oleic acid surfactant and PEG dispersion medium.

The particles for fluids were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and their crystal phase and magnetic properties were analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and measured by vibrating sample magnetometry (VSM), respectively. The viscosity of the fluids was measured using Brookfield viscometer. In order to apply an external magnetic field, two pieces of the permanent magnet ($\Phi 50 \times T 10$ mm, 3.5

kG) were placed on either side of 400 ml beaker filled with about 300 ml of the fluid. The field gradient was approximately 550 G at the center.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Preparation of ferromagnetic fluid

Since the reaction formula for coprecipitation of the magnetic particles is practically

the ratio of weight of core particles to fluid volume 80 ml is 25 mg/ml from the magnetite formation of $0.00865 \text{ mol} \times 231.54 \text{ g/mol} = 2.0 \text{ g}$. In such a fluid concentration, the surface of the magnetite particles can be sufficiently covered with 0.004 mol (1.13 g) of the oleic acid (d: 0.891). Therefore, the amount of 90 % oleic acid added becomes 1.41 ml from the following calculation,

$$X_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 0.126 \text{ g with } 1.13 / (1.13 + X_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}) = 0.9 \rightarrow \\ (1.13 + 0.126) / 0.891 = 1.41 \text{ ml}$$

The precipitated particles were typically spherical with the mean diameter of 12 nm[6]. In Fig. 2, the XRD results reveal that the crystal phase of the coprecipitated or oleic acid-adsorbed nanoparticles corresponds to magnetite. Figure 3 shows that such particles are superparamagnetic. The magnetization values measured in the field range of ± 1000 Oe was 37 emu/g for the bare particles and 23 emu/g for the particles covered with the nonmagnetic organic layer.

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of as-precipitated particles and oleic acid-adsorbed particles. The peak indexes indicate crystal planes of magnetite phase.

Fig. 3. Magnetization curves of as-precipitated and oleic acid-adsorbed ferromagnetic nanoparticles.

3.2 Preparation of magnetorheological fluid

The particles prepared by top-down method, in general, are coarse and nonuniform compared with those by bottom-up method. For the purpose of improving a poor dispersibility of the particles in the magnetorheological fluid, PEG-400 (average 120 mPa·s at 20 °C) two times as high as PEG-200 in viscosity was used as the dispersion medium. 2 g (37 mmol) of the ball-milled Fe-6.5wt%Si powder was mixed separately with 2 g (18.5 mmol), 1 g (9.25 mmol) and 0.5 g (4.63 mmol) of trimethylamine N-oxide dehydrate to obtain the optimum oxidation ratio. The mixtures in 100 ml of H₂O were surface-oxidized by stirring with 300 rpm for 2 h at 100 °C and then washed thoroughly to remove the remaining TMANO. The succeeding process was accompanied with the same conditions as applied for the ferromagnetic fluid. The disperse state in PEG of the differently oxidized particles was very similar, in which the layer separation into floating particles, dispersed solution and precipitate occurred while the prepared fluids were left all the day alone. The reason why some particles float and coagulate is that the particle size of the milled powder is widely distributed from 20 nm up to 1,000 nm, as shown in Fig. 4. Accordingly, it is suggested that in the case using fine particles milled mechanically as a disperse matter, the particles need to be sorted by size by separation process.

Figure 5 shows the saturation magnetization for the oxidation particles obtained at different mole ratios of TMANO to bare particles in the field range of ± 10 kOe. 151 emu/g for the as-milled bare particles was steeply decreased to 71 emu/g with 0.125 as a mole ratio which was slightly fluctuated to 93 and 78 emu/g with the ratios of 0.25 and 0.50,

respectively. However, it is noted that all the values for the oxidized particles are about the same within the error limit of ± 10 % for the magnetization measurement. In view of this trend in oxidation state of the particles, the surface of the bare particles needs to be treated with the smallest possible amount of oxidizing agent. Figure 6 shows the process for preparing the magnetorheological fluids.

In Fig. 7, the magnetization curve of surface-oxidized particles was compared with the curves of oleic acid-adsorbed particles and oleic acid-PEG-adsorbed particles at the oxidation condition of mole ratio 0.125. The saturation magnetization of the oxidized particles was decreased from 71 emu/g to 50 emu/g with the layer of oleic acid and to 40 emu/g with the bilayer of oleic acid and PEG. The magnetization values of the oxidized particles and the oleic acid-adsorbed particles in the field of 1 kOe were 53 and 37 emu/g, respectively, which were much higher than 37 and 23 emu/g for the corresponding ferromagnetic particles. All of the magnetorheological particles exhibited a very small coercive force of about 88 Oe.

Fig. 4. SEM image of attrition-milled, heat-treated and then ball-milled Fe-6.5wt%Si particles.

Fig. 5. Saturation magnetization(M_s) of Fe-6.5wt%Si particles oxidized at various mole ratios of trimethylamine N-oxide dihydrate to bare particles.

Fig. 6. A process flow for magnetorheological fluids prepared with milled Fe-6.5wt%Si particles, oleic acid surfactant and PEG dispersion medium.

Fig. 7. Magnetization curves for surface-oxidized, oleic acid-adsorbed and oleic acid-PEG-adsorbed Fe-6.5wt%Si particles at 0.125 as mole ratio of trimethylamine N-oxide dihydrate to bare particles.

3.3 Bonding mechanism

The water-based magnetic fluids have been usually prepared by forming a bilayer on particles, sometimes with oleic acid as the first surfactant and sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate as the second surfactant. In this work, the magnetic particles were dispersed into PEG medium using only an oleic acid as the surfactant, because the PEG can be also applied on the particles as an outlayer together with the fatty acid[7]. The hydrophilic fluids were successfully obtained by adding oleic acid to the

mixture of magnetic particles and PEG and stirring it at 100 °C.

From the structural viewpoint, iron oxide of the particle surface is partially negative-charged and both molecules of oleic acid and PEG have a polar group of -OH. Therefore, the shell formation can proceed from the polar bond between a hydrogen atom in carboxyl group of oleic acid and an oxygen atom on the surface of particles, the physical bond by van der Waals forces between nonpolar groups in the first layer and the second layer of oleic acid, and the chemical bond due to the ester formation reaction of carboxyl group in the second oleic acid layer with hydrogen in the end of PEG molecular chain. The water accompanied by the esterification is mostly removed by vaporizing at the process temperature of 100 °C. This molecular bonding is schematically represented in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Bonding parts in a fluid system of iron oxide particles, oleic acid and polyethylene glycol.

3.4 Viscosity and shear strength of fluids

Since the particles of magnetorheological fluid are mostly coarser than those of ferromagnetic fluid, the former, in general, exhibits high viscosity and yield stress compared to the latter under a magnetic field. Therefore, in order to effectively compare the viscosity of the ferromagnetic fluid with that of the other fluid, the ferromagnetic fluids were applied with the concentration of 50 mg/ml instead of the existing 25 mg/ml. The viscosity of the fluids was measured at room temperature to exclude the influence of temperature on viscous flow. The measurement of viscosity was carried out after homogeneously dispersing more than 10 min. The fluid particles and the magnetic field was applied so as not to influence on a metal tip of the viscometer.

Figure 9 shows the viscosity of ferromagnetic fluid and magnetorheological fluid measured with and without field. The viscosity was increased to 57 cP by 6.7 times in the ferromagnetic fluid and to 160 cP by 11.5 times in the magnetorheological fluid with an effect of the external magnetic field. In comparison of the magnetorheological fluid to the

ferromagnetic fluid, the viscosity values were 2.8 times with magnetic field and 1.6 times without field.

In Table 1, the shear strength was obtained with the related numerical values for each fluid. The shear strength of magnetorheological fluid went up tenfold by applying the field and was about treble of the strength of ferromagnetic fluid under the field. With such an applied field, increase ratio of the shear strength in the magnetorheological fluid was high by one and a half times compared with that in the ferromagnetic fluid.

Fig. 9. Viscosity factors of ferromagnetic and magnetorheological fluids measured with and without an external magnetic field.

Table 1. Shear strength of magnetic fluid and magnetorheological fluid obtained with and without an external magnetic field.

Fluid type	Ferro-magnetic	Magneto-rheological
Shear strength without field (kPa)	0.57	1.12
Shear strength with field (kPa)	3.85	10.7
Increase ratio of shear strength (%)	670	960

4. Conclusions

Magnetite nanoparticles for the ferromagnetic fluid and fine particles of Fe-6.5wt%Si alloy for the magnetorheological fluid were produced by bottom-up method and top-down method, respectively. The hydrophilic magnetic fluids were prepared with the surfactant of oleic acid and the dispersion medium of polyethylene glycol. The dispersion of fine Fe-6.5wt%Si particles into polyethylene glycol was

achieved by adsorbing oleic acid on the surface of oxidized particles. The viscosity of ferromagnetic fluids and magnetorheological fluids was measured before and after applying an external magnetic field, from which the shear strength was evaluated. In proportion to the measured viscosity values, the shear strength of magnetorheological fluid with an applied field was approximately 10 times as high as the strength of magnetorheological fluid with no field and was nearly 3 times compared with the strength of ferromagnetic fluid at the same condition. This improvement of shear strength in the magnetorheological fluid can reflect effectively the resistibility against a strong impact.

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